

Managing Community Development Programs for Productivity through Adult Education: Agenda for Citizens' Participation in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper focuses on managing adult education towards community development with emphasis on the inclusion of citizens' active participation in Nigeria. It discusses community development programmes through adult education and its relevance in conscientizing and mobilizing the citizens towards participating and engaging in community development activities. Programmes of activities such as; literacy education, vocational education, health education, agricultural education amongst others are responsible for raising human skills, knowledge and promote quality engagement towards sustainable development in Nigeria. The study employed secondary source of information and further contends that citizens' participation in community development could be propelled through adult education programme in Nigeria. The study concludes that citizens' participation in any community development is vital to improving their living standard, enhance productivity and reduce poverty, ignorance and illiteracy within the society. On the bases of these, the paper recommends that managing adult education towards community development in Nigeria implies but not limited to all-inclusiveness of the citizens who identify what constitute development and work toward achieving it for the overall wellbeing of the populace.

Keyword: Management, Community Development, Adult Education, Participation

Introduction

One important strategy for effective community development is the participation in rural development efforts involving diverse citizens to form a common front within the community. In this aspect Cohen and Uphoft in Okafor and Onukwu (2022) conceived participation to mean the involvement of a significant number of persons in situation or actions which enhance their wellbeing. They posit participation as the active process in which a people in question take part in the initiative and implementation of decision. Participation therefore, refers to the ability of individuals to make impute into the decision making process and play a vital role in improving the quality of life in the community and the society.

Consequently, community development programmes involve and include job employment, identification of health needs, economic empowerment in which the people are in partnership with those able to assist them identify their needs and increasingly assume the responsibility to plan, manage, control, and assess the collective actions that are necessary for community development to strive (Esuefieni,2020).Citizens' participation becomes imperative as it can only be achieved when individuals are sensitized and informed about the need to engage in community development programmes. Adult education becomes a resource development because it is an organized learning activities arranged within an organization in order to improve performance or personal growth for the purpose of improving the job, the individual, or the society where the person lives (Bello, 2022).

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Education serves as a bridge that links an individual and his community, reduces unemployment and fasten community development. Seya (2014) opts that investment in the development of human capital through education (adult education) is crucial for developing a labour force and managerial know-how able to compete to today's global economy. Invariably, adult education contributes to human capital development of individuals and instill in them managerial skills to participate in the development of their communities. Development in this instance can only be made possible if it is human centered process and this can only be achieved through adult education programmes. Adult education programmes provide literacy education, vocational skills and knowledge relevant to developing a community; this is why Okafor (2022) stated that adult education is the most needed education because it helps communities to be easily mobilized toward their development for their survival and their future generation.

Therefore, community development as seen by Akintayo and Oghenekohwo (2004) cited in Okafor (2022) is a mechanism and a process which must arouse the interest of the community members as to participate in community development activities. The community members must be first sensitized about the need to participate in community development programme as it affects their individual and community wellbeing. Bello (2021) states that managing adult education to achieve its set objectives and goals involve inclusiveness of the citizens to partake in the processes, programmes and activities for effective development of the individual and the community. Ebisine (2015) opts that management is the process of supervising, coordinating and organizing the activities of people in an organization to achieve results not achievable without planning, supervision, coordination, and organization. Adult education is targeted to improving adults towards acquiring vocational skills, economic empowerment; improve literacy and sustainable development which require good managers who will act as change agents. Managing community development programmes through adult education will proffer solvable solutions hindering community development and productivity due to lack of citizens' participation. Therefore, the nucleus of the study is to find out how adult education programmes will enhance citizens' participation and promote community development in Nigeria.

Adult Education Programmes in Nigeria

Adult education has been defined, seen and acknowledged by different authors, practitioners, and stakeholders based on their philosophical perspectives. Chijioke (2010) as cited in Okafor and Onukwu (2020) sees adult education as the practice of teaching and educating adults. Okafor and Arikawei (2020) citing Rogers opined that adult education comprises "all planned and purposeful learning opportunities offered to those who are recognized and recognize themselves as adult in their own community and in the formal (initial education system or who have passed beyond the possible state of initial education if they are not in it), whether such opportunities treat the learners as adults in decision making, use of appropriate adult learning methodology and style and purpose and to meet their own needs'. In a more comprehensive definition of adult education, Seya (2014) believes that it is a transmission process of general, technical or vocational knowledge, as well as skills, values and attitudes, which takes place out of the formal education system with a view to remedying early education inadequacies of matured people or equipping them with the knowledge and cultural elements required for their self-fulfillment and active participation in the social, and community development amongst others.

Adult education as an academic field of study is saddled with the responsibility of solving socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental problems. According to Owede (2022) adult education offers opportunities that help adult learners to acquire relevant knowledge and skills including information and attitudinal change for immediate application to address prevailing human and community

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development problems. Adult education is a veritable instrument for transmitting knowledge, competences and skills. It is also an empowerment that promotes self-determined bottom-up development of communities and individuals through active citizenship and social inclusion. Therefore, adult education fills the inadequacies or lack of education. Education and mostly adult education is a path to enlightenment and plays a key role in improving the functional role of individuals in a community (Okafor and Arikawei, 2020).

Knowles, Elwood and Swanson (2015) adduce that the dynamics of adult education (through non-formal) lays in the potentials of social transformation to individual beneficiaries in character, skills, literacy, political participation and community development activities. In his own assertion Asiyai (2015) states that obtaining a quality education is the foundation to improving citizens' lives and sustainable development as it is only quality education that can sharpen the minds of the individuals and helps transform the society economically, socially and politically. In this circumstance, Hussain (2013) opts that adult education programmes (community development inclusive) confirm increased levels of self-esteem and high levels of knowledge and skills which encourage positive and active engagement of people in their own development and wellbeing. Adult education should be transformed and managed to incorporate citizens' participation and engagement in community development of their communities. It is a human driving force geared toward solving the numerous cultural, political, educational, and socio-economic problems hindering human development. For Onyenemezu (2012), education is a means to provide a balanced individual capable of surviving in his environment and contributing meaningfully towards the survival of that society he belongs. Therefore, it becomes a tool that equip individual to improve himself and make him socially and politically relevant.

It is in this regard that Ekuri, Betiang, Andong and Eyam (2022) state that adult education is the fertilizer needed for development and democracy to take root and grow. It is the invisible ingredient in any successful strategy for eradicating poverty, illiteracy, superstition, and achieving gender equality. It is a mechanized instrument that exposes and empowers beneficiaries to be on their own, contribute towards their children education and mostly participate in community development (Ekuri et. al., 2022). It proffers solutions to all human socio-economic, political, religious, and community underdevelopment. Adult education is an education that is programmed to conscientize, sensitize and re-direct adults of a community towards solving their immediate problems for community wellbeing and development.

Community Development Programmes in Nigeria

The term community development has been a concept since the beginning of the world. It is a process where community members come together to identify their felt-needs, partake in community participation and engagement, assemblage of human, financial and material resources towards solving the identified felt-needs for community welfare and upliftment. It is on this premise that Frank and Smith (2013) see it as a gathering where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems. Okafor and Onukwu (2022) citing Chukwueze submitted that development programme is a process whereby the efforts of the community are combined with the efforts of the governmental authorities to improve the living condition of the people thereby encouraging development of various human potentials within the community. According to Powell and Geoghegan cited in Okafor (2022) community development is described as an interactive process of knowledge and action designed to change conditions which marginalize communities and groups and is underpinned by a vision of self-help and community self-reliance. It is because community development has being a process since the beginning of the world that Onyekwelu (2018) states that there has being vigorous indigenous efforts to

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improve the welfare of the communities in various parts of the country with little dependent on the government or donor agencies. It shows that community development does not thrive on individuals, government, and, or, donor agencies but identified felt-needs of the community. This captures community development as a phenomenal mechanism and a system which must promote the interest of the community members to participate in community development.

Obetta and Charity (2012) as cited in Okafor and Onukwu (2022) submitted that substantial participation and sustained interest could only be achieved through community development efforts of the people and in direct consonance with the people's social, cultural, and religious values. In another development Etigbamo (2013) believes that it is a deliberate plan of action undertaken by an individual or group of persons with the active participation of the members of the community with or without the support of external agencies in order to bring about economic, social, political, technological, and cultural improvements in the overall living condition of the people of the community. In this narrative, community development is aimed at providing and promoting better living conditions for the entire community members, relying on their resources, initiatives and active involvement and engagement. To enhance participation towards development, a systematic policy of mobilization of the community people in the developmental outlook is imperative. The focus on active participation, involvement, and engagement of people on the issues which affect their lives; should be directed towards encouraging empowerment, self-help, and sharing skill, knowledge and experience (Okafor and Onukwu, 2020).

Therefore, community development becomes a strategy or approach for improvement that is directed towards the upliftment of community members to a better living. Community development provides better living standard to the people. It is on this base that Okafor (2022) citing Sander opined that community development is a process moving from stage to stage, a method of working towards a goal; a programme of procedures and as a movement sweeping people up in emotion and belief. He argued that community development means better living both materially and socially. He further stated that it is a process whereby people are taught to improve themselves not only by doing things together but also by planning together with a view to providing the actual technique for doing the job or finding suitable solution to their problems. In this circumstances therefore, community development can be conceptualized as a change process causing improvement to life activities and programmes, and social relations that aim to meeting the needs and aspirations of people of similar historical and cultural heritage living together to reduce complete dependence on external sustainability (Bello,2022).

Community development is one major modern traditional heritage in Africa, Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008) as cited in Etigbamo (2020) agree that it is a flourishing heritage in African societies involving community citizen engagement. They stated that it is an indigenous mechanism and technique developed and employed by the people to identify their felt-needs, choose what they want and take cooperative actions to satisfy their needs. Okafor and Onukwu (2022) opt that community development relies on the interaction between people's joint actions rather than individual activities. This is the reason why development involves active participation of all the citizens within the community. Therefore community development becomes a process whereby people are taught to improve themselves not only by doing things together but also by planning together with a view to providing the actual technique for doing the job or finding suitable solution to their problems (Bello, 2022).

Community Development Programmes for Productivity in Nigeria

Community development as a component unit of adult education is very useful for sustainable development of any community, society or nation. The developmental programmes which enhance

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citizens' productivity are various but not limited to these: literacy education, vocational acquisition skills, community education, agricultural extension education, cooperative societies, health education, amongst others.

Literacy Education: literacy education is an inseparable part of development and the rights of every citizen. The ability of every individual to acquire the skills of reading, writing, and computation transform and mobilize the people to participate actively in their self-help projects which transform to national development. According to Bello (2022) citing Imhabekhai the desire and ability to read, write, and compute materials promote productivity and enhance development in any society. It enables the recipients (adults) to understand higher concepts of development and productivity which maintain a sustainable community development.

Vocational Education: Adult vocational education is conceived in the context that at the end of the training the beneficiaries must have successfully acquire a skill which will enable them (adults) to be self-sustaining and, or improve their productivity where such adults are employed. This is why Egunu, Akpotohwo and Ogeibiri (2017) believe that it is designed to prepare individual or skilled personnel for an occupation, a trade or a job. Therefore, vocational education is tailored to enhance citizens' engagement and participation for productivity at the end of programme participation.

Community Education: Community education programme is hinged on the premise that the consciousness of people themselves plays a vital role in affecting positive change (Bello, 2022). He maintained that community education will affect change in attitude, skill, ways of participating in community development programmes and knowledge of contemporary issues. Bello (2022) opts that it is educational process that involves community mobilization for development and sustains wellbeing of the people.

Agricultural Extension Education: Most communities in Nigeria are mostly subsistence farmers who hardly produce enough for family consumption due to analog equipment and lack of modern mechanized method of farming. In order to change this crude method of farming, Bello (2022) citing Ezimah states that agricultural extension education service provides a sound base for rural development. He maintained that extension is conceived as the development of the individual, community members, and the rural society as a continuous education process for productivity and better living of the citizens.

Health Education: The most significant ingredience for any development is health. It is therefore one of the cardinal required basic social needs of the rural communities. This is because health services have being the driving force for community development. Health education becomes imperative for health delivery designed to mobilize the rural citizens to participate and cooperate in the task of health care delivery for community development (Nnabuihe, Emenike and Odunze, 2017). In view of the importance of community health services and development, Ibama and Dennis (2016) opt that community health and natural development are inextricably tied together, in which the evaluation of national development cannot be complete without community health component. Health education is primarily meant to cater for the health existence of the citizens, which will increase their effective participation in national life and their increased productive capacity.

Cooperative Societies: Cooperative societies are important tools for real transformation of communities. They assist members to pull their resources together hence ensuring sustainable business enterprise and wellbeing of the people. Bello (2022) citing Dokubo says that it is very essential that cooperators work with other like-minded people in groups to make a meaningful achievements not only satisfying the basic human needs but also raising the conditions of living of the rural people to acceptable standards.

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According to Baarda in Bello (2022) cooperative societies is a collective action in which individuals join together to accomplish what would be more costly or impossible to achieve individually. Cooperative organizations by their nature serve as an effective development vehicle; they build economic self-reliance and development (Akpan, 2015).

Managing Adult Education and Community Development for Citizens' Participation in Nigeria

Management is the whole process which involves the control of human, material and financial resources to achieve a set goal and objectives. Okafor and Onukwu (2020) cited Nigeria Institute of Management stated that management is the process of planning, organizing, leading, controlling, directing, staffing, and channeling efforts and resources to achieve planned goals. In another development, Bayefa (2020) citing Peretomode opined that management is the guidance, leadership and control of the efforts of a group of people towards some common objectives. Okafor and Onukwu (2020) see management of education (adult education inclusive) as a process of human engineering of a leader with the capacity to produce and nourish ideas, stipulate thought, motivate action, introduce and manage resources and change in education. They further stated that management of adult education implies holding and practicing managerial skills, determination and courage in taking responsibility for the implementation of changes that trigger progress, development and performance in the process of training adult learners towards community engagement and participation. Therefore managing adult education requires all-inclusive citizens' participation in order to achieve the goal of community development. The goal of citizen participation is to move from where one is to where one wants to be in terms of sustainable community development and wellbeing.

Development either political, social, economic, and or educational cannot take place without basic education. Education as a social amenity must be accessible, free and at the reach of both the young, and the old so that they can play their developmental role. It is due to the imperative nature of development that Adekola and Abanum in Okafor and Arikaiwei (2020) state that the only difference between the developed and undeveloped countries are related to the level of literacy among the populace. Therefore for the citizens to participate actively in community development, they must be integrated in decision making, planning, execution, and at the same time must have acquired certain degree of education. The most adoring and interesting aspect of education as stated by Gbesoevi (2019) is that education is a process of training and developing the knowledge, skill, mind and character of people. He further stated that education can as well be seen as the process by which latent abilities of individual are developed so that they can be useful to themselves and the society at large. It is an institution that enables individuals to think freely and rationally which makes social progress, development and innovation possible.

Seya (2014) opines that investment in the development of human capital through adult education is crucial for developing a labour force and managerial know-how able to compete in today's global economy. Adult education as an educational institution helps to instill in the citizens managerial skills which enable adults or the beneficiaries to participate in the development of their communities. Education (formal, informal and non-formal) is the best option for developing a community using the citizens. In this circumstance adult education is the most needed education due to it helps community citizens to be easily mobilized and conscientized towards contributing in their own development for their survival and their future generation (Okafor, 2022). Community development as one of the principles of community felt-need must be made all citizens' inclusiveness if it is made human- centered programme.

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The concept of citizens' participation states that people are ready and willing to participate in activities and projects that will help them improve their lives and the community. Citizens' participation is a systematic way of freely involving community members to identify and profile solutions to their needs and that of their communities. McCloskey, et al (2015) posits that participation involves planning, generation of ideas, decision making, and sharing responsibility to community members. This is why Kobani and Alozie (2019) believe that community development is channeled towards enhancing people's capacity to solve their problems through organizational structures that promote citizens' voluntary participation in self- help projects. Adult education comes handy because it is a veritable instrument to promote a sense of cohesion, purpose, and achievement among members of the community (Babatunde, 2022).

Community as a legal entity is made up of man (youths, women and men) and development cannot be possible without the active involvement, engagement and participation of all the citizens. It is a pretense, according to (Emeh, Eluwa and Ukah, 2012) as cited in Okafor and Onukwu (2022) to believe that development could occur in a community without active engagement of the people, particularly the large number of citizens who reside in the community. Abiona (2009), Imhabekhai (2009) and Okafor and Onukwu (2022) opined that the principle of citizen's participation is the hub of all other principles of community development. They further stated that the principle implies that the people in the community should take part in the identification of needs, planning, execution, utilization and evaluation of programmes and projects. Therefore community development could be a mirage without the collective involvement, engagement, and participation of citizens towards solving their felt-need. Okafor and Onukwu (2022) argued that substantial participation and sustained interest in community development could only be achieved based on educational, cultural, and religious values of the people. To enhance participation, mobilization and engagement towards community development, a systematic policy of mobilizing the citizens in the development outlook is imperative. It is therefore, a process moving from stage to stage; a method of working towards a goal, a programme of procedure, and as a movement sweeping people up in emotion and belief (Okafor, 2022).

Owede (2022) insists that adult education plays a key role in sustainable development and promotes economic, social, and environmental dimensions of community development creating a favourable conditions for empowering active citizens. This is as a result of the functionality of adults as managers of resources (human and material) which are dependent on knowledge and skills which can be properly provided by adults and adult education programmes (Rogers, 2016). Adult education is a trigger of human development and sustainable development in both communities and on any other levels.

Conclusion

Citizens' participation in any development programme is vital for productivity and sustainability. This is because community development is one sure way of improving the overall living conditions of the citizens in any society especially those in the rural communities. Adult education which is one of the components of education encourages citizens on the need for community participation, enhances citizens' skills and knowledge, mobilizes and sensitizes the populace on the way to manage and improve their human, material and financial resources towards the betterment of individuals and their communities. It also highlights and enlightens the citizens on some of the community development programmes such like

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literacy education, vocational training, skill acquisition, and health education amongst others which promote productivity and wellbeing of the people. Hence, the need for all citizens of a community to be actively involved from the planning stage to the physical execution of community felt-projects to ensure completion and sustainability of community development programmes.

Recommendations

Based on the reviewed literature, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is the need for all-inclusiveness of the adult citizens to participate in community development programmes in their communities to enhance productivity and wellbeing.
2. Education in Nigeria is so broad that there is a need that Ministry of Adult Education be created to take over the management and administration of adult education programmes in Nigeria.
3. The utilitarian value and nature of adult education in improving the living standard of adults, reduction of poverty, ignorance and illiteracy among others cannot be overemphasized. Therefore, there is the need for adults to be conscientized and sensitized to participate actively in adult education programmes in Nigeria.
4. Adult education professionals and qualified adult educators should be engaged to manage and administer community development programmes for community sustainable development.

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